

Open Schools Journal for Open Science

Vol. 3, 2020

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<https://doi.org/10.12681/osj.23357>

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To cite this article:

Baka, A., Ntorli, V., & Argyri, P. (2020). Animal rights. *Open Schools Journal for Open Science*, 3(3).
doi:<https://doi.org/10.12681/osj.23357>

Animal rights

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Abstract

Most of educational projects are related with challenges of environmental issues and rarely taking under consideration that animals are part of life of land. Animals have a strong effect in our lives, as keep the life cycle balances. That is why in our project we decided to concern ourselves with Animal Rights, all around the world and in Greece. The main problems we are dealing with are: The living conditions of productive animals, the rights of stray animals, the abuse of animals, the torture of equine animals and animals which produce fur, the conduct of experimental medical tests on animals and the protection of endangered animals. In our project we have set some goals as well as the means of meeting them. When it comes to finding a solution to the problems mentioned above, after noticing what our classmates knew about them, we came to the realization that what is needed most of all is better information about these problems that can be found in an easy, fun and interactive platform. As a team, we made various games and activities with which people can learn about animals and the difficult situations they are dealing with.

Keywords

Animal rights, protection, endangered, productive animals, fur, abuse

Theoretical framework; Based on conducted researches

In order to understand the possible legal framework to which we are referring as well as the recent developments regarding the issue in Greece, we recorded some articles of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food which are directly related to the questions our interviewee was asked.

How do you think the number of stray animals will decrease?

Article 9(1) from the Public Consultation of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food on the Draft Law "For dominant and stray pets and the protection of animals from exploitation or use for profit purposes": Municipalities are required to ensure the collection and management of stray pets, in accordance with this Article. This work can also be carried out by animal welfare associations and associations, in cooperation with the competent Municipality.

Article 9(4) from the Public Consultation of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food on the Draft Law 'For dominant and stray pets and the protection of animals from exploitation or use for profit purposes': *Stray pets collected are driven in part to the existing shelters of stray pets, municipal vets or private vets, which have the appropriate infrastructure and can accommodate temporary and temporary for a reasonable amount of time the animals to be treated, until they are treated, undergo a veterinary examination, sterilized, marked by electronic labelling, as strays and recorded on the online electronic basis.*

Where should one look in order to adopt an animal?

Article 4(1) from the Public Consultation of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food on the Draft Law 'For dominant and stray pets and the protection of animals from exploitation or use for profit purposes': *The Information Technology Department of the Ministry of Information Technology creates an Online Electronic Basis for the marking and registration of pets and their owners. The Online Electronic Base shall record, by the certified veterinarians, the data relating to the identification of the paminted pets and the identification of their owner.*

Are animals given away?

Article 6 Paragraph 1 of the Public Consultation of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food on the Draft Law 'On Domestic and Stray Pet Animals and the Protection of Animals from the Use or Use for Profit': *The natural or legal person or association of persons for the purpose of commercially raising, breeding or selling pet animals must obtain a permit issued by the Directorate General of Regional Agricultural Economics and Veterinary of the Region in which he resides.*

Article 5 Paragraph 6 of the Public Consultation of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food on the Draft Law 'On Domestic and Stray Pet Animals and the Protection of Animals from the Use or Use for Profit': *The publication of this law prohibits the publication of pet ads for adoption or free concession or sale on brochures, brochures, or websites unless their electronic signature number is indicated.*

What are the needs of pets? Does the law help?

Article 5 Paragraph 1 of the Public Consultation of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food on the Draft Law 'On Domesticated and Strayed Animals and the Protection of Animals from the Use or Use for Profit':

The owner of the dominant pet must:

- (a) Ensure the marking and registration of his animal.*
- (b) Comply with the animal welfare rules and ensure that it is subject to at least an annual veterinary examination.*
- (c) Be provided with the pet's health booklet or passport for each pet animal.*
- (d) Not abandon his animal.*
- (e) Ensure that the animal's faces are immediately cleaned of the environment.*

What about productive animals? Do they have rights?

Article 5 Paragraph 1 of the Integrated Public Consultation of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food on the Draft Law 'Arrangements for the Establishment and Operation of Livestock Installations': *All kinds of new livestock establishments are established and operate beyond residential areas (cities, towns, villages, settlements)*

Article 5 Paragraph 2 of the Integrated Public Consultation of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food on the Draft Law 'Arrangements for the Establishment and Operation of Livestock Installations': *The minimum area of land required for the construction of livestock facilities is determined by the provisions of Articles 6, 7 and 8 of Law 1577/1985 "General Building Regulations" (A`140) and the specific provisions of the town planning legislation applicable at all times.*

Article 5 Paragraph 3 of the Integrated Public Consultation of the Ministry of Rural Development and Food on the Draft Law 'Arrangements for the Establishment and Operation of Livestock Installations': *The minimum distances between livestock establishments and sites or activities in*

need of protection are set out in Annex 1 to Article 19 of this Act and have a two-way validity, in the sense that they apply in the same way in cases where the area where legally operating livestock already operates.

European legal framework.

Article 13 of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union

In formulating and implementing the Union's agriculture, fisheries, transport, internal market, research and technological development and space policies, the Union and the Member States shall, since animals are sentient beings, pay full regard to the welfare requirements of animals, while respecting the legislative or administrative provisions and customs of the Member States relating in particular to religious rites, cultural traditions and regional heritage.

Directives vs. regulations in the EU legal order

In the European Union's legal order, directives are applicable to Member States which have to transpose them into their own national legal system, with the possibility to go beyond the minimum rules laid down in an EU directive. By contrast, regulations are directly applicable to citizens and businesses, without being transformed into national laws. They usually establish common standards and restrict the possibility for the Member States to adopt standards other than those laid down in a regulation. Member States however, still have to establish sanctions in their national legal order.

All over the world, billions of animals are bred in cages. This includes pigs, hens, rabbits, ducks and quail - which are obliged to live under severe pressure in cages. Sows are forced to breastfeed their piglets in crates, rabbits and quail endure their entire lives in barren cages, and ducks and geese are placed in cages and fed great amounts of food in order to produce foie gras. These systems restrict, restrict and prevent animals from expressing their physical behaviors.

The European Union (EU) recognizes productive animals as living beings. However, tens of billions of animals suffer short, sordid lives on factory farms, where the priority is profit above all else.

To save space, factories like such are full of garbage and cages, preventing ordinary behaviors such as nesting or feeding. This often causes animals to cause injuries to themselves due to frustration and stress.

The use of antibiotics to promote the development of agricultural animals is outlawed in the EU but is legal in some countries. In the United States, approximately 80% of all antibiotics are believed to be used in productive animals [4] [5] [6].

Animals used in experiments

The USDA/APHIS published the 2016 animal survey statistics. Overall, the number of animals (covered by the Animal Welfare Act) used in the US survey increased by 6.9% from 767,622 (2015) to 820,812 (2016). This includes both public and private institutions.

These statistics do not include all animals, as most mice, rats and fish are not covered by the Animal Welfare Act - although they are still covered by other regulations that protect the welfare of Animals. Also, the 137,444 animals kept in research facilities in 2016 were not included but did not participate in research studies.

Statistics show that 52% of research is conducted on guinea pigs, hamsters and rabbits, 10% on farm animals, while 11% on dogs or cats and 9% on non-human primates. In the United Kingdom, where mice, rats, fish and birds are counted in the annual statistics, more than 97% of the survey concerns rodents, birds and fish [3].

Stray Animals and animals that produce fur

The abuse of stray animals in our country at all levels remains intense. In urban centers a reduction in their abuse incidents can be spotted, while they remain at the same levels in the province. About 2 million people in Greece own an animal. One in five privately owned animals is abused with intent or ignorance. Phobes are unfortunately the most serious danger to the lives of stray animals. Every year 6 to 8 million people are spent on the project. Annually approximately 6-8 million dogs and cats are being taken to shelters in Europe, of which 3-4 million are euthanized for not being adopted at their specified period of stay. [8]

Globally, we must also take into account the different value that some animals have in certain cultures. A typical example is that of the case of dogs. In the US and UK for example dogs are considered a kind and friendly pet ideal for all homes. In contrast, in many Muslim country's dogs are believed to be dirty and dangerous animals that endanger the public health of the state. Therefore, understanding different cultures can lead us to find a common ground so as to solve problems such as the increasing number of strays on the streets, animal experiments, etc. [7]

Mink, foxes, chinchilla, etc. They are brutally killed every year in fur farms using methods such as electric shock and poisoning. No law yet in the U.S. has placed restrictions and laws on the protection of these animals.

In Greece there are farms made for fur animals mainly in Kozani and Kastoria. Which in 2011 reached the number of 43 fur farms, in 2014 105, 123 in 2017, 131 in 2018 and finally in 2019 they are reduced to 112. [9]

Research framework

Objectives

After gathering and knowing all this information, we came to the conclusion that people don't seem to regard the rights of animals as a serious problem, due to the absence of scientifically proven facts that prove that the rights of animals are not being respected by people. These pieces of information were very impactful for us, so we tried to set some goals which we are going to tackle through raising awareness about the issue

The main goal we have set is to convince people that we should treat animals with absolute respect of their rights. However, as our main goal is too abstract, we set some mini goals too, which are the following:

1. Protection of endangered animals. More and more animals are being put into the endangered animal species list, and for the nature to function properly, it is really important to not let any of these animals go extinct.
2. Encouragement to help stray animals live a decent life. We should all remember that stray animals have needs too, just like any other being. They crave water, food, a stable place to stay and the feeling of being loved by someone, as well as everyone else so we should treat them with respect and help them when we can.
3. To reduce or even eliminate fur industries and the torture of equine animals. The production of fur is known to be a blood lustful and torturous industry, due to all the animals being killed for us to wear something as trivial as fur coats. This way we hope to encourage people not to buy any animal-torture related products.
4. Reduce medical experiments conducted on animals. We believe that not more or less animals that are needed to make sure that a tested medicine is safe for humans to consume should be used in such experiments. When either one of the two happens, it is considered to be an unsuccessful experiment. So, we ask of scientists to be sure of the exact number of animals they are going to need and not waste any more lives in vain.
5. Claiming better living conditions for productive animals. Despite being raised to be slaughtered and eaten it is natural for humans to crave to eat meat. However, what we ask of people is to restrict the portions of meat they consume and for animals that live in factories to be considered as beings that have the right to live a decent life.
6. Reducing animal abuse. As we presented in the data before, many people are still abusing their pets or animals in general. We, as a team, wholeheartedly wish that the law against the abuse of animals will be more strictly enforced.

Methodology

To understand more about animal rights, an interview was held with a president of an animal welfare association. Our interviewee accepted happily to help us with our cause; however, they asked to remain anonymous so that this interview is not regarded as an advertisement for their association. The interview was held over the phone and lasted for about 1 hour. Full interview (question and replies included in Appendix 1).

Our team picked the following questions because through them we can understand how most animal welfare associations work and the issues they try to tackle. Additionally, we can also see the solutions they have provided as well as some general advice for the average person. To sum up, the aim of this interview is to learn more information on how various people have tried to solve some of the problems we mention in our “abstract” category and to explain some misconceptions about the proper care of animals.

Results

Basic conclusions by interview

Animal welfare associations try to help stray and hurt animals, organize events about their important work, educate various kids in schools about the hardships of animals and they have representatives in office that can fight for better legislation when it comes to these issues. Supposedly, the municipality should sterilize as many stray animals as they can. Moreover, more illegal breeders should be arrested. Animals in pet stores are closed in cages and are left to die slowly and alone. Animals need to be taken care and not be purchased as a quick and easy gift. The problem is that the rules exist but no one checks if they are really enforced. Social media and traditional media are known to sometimes overdramatize situations to get more clicks and attention. More often than not, the real problem is the behavior of certain humans with unresolved psychological problems that they project to animals. Productive animals are deprived of one thing most people would not be able to live without: freedom. The freedom to walk, the freedom to eat whenever and whatever they want to, the freedom to make their own decisions and explore the world. Ultimately, productive animals have lost their right to live a normal and healthy life. Doing simple stuff like contacting an animal association and generally having an empathetic behavior when approached by animals can make a change.

Proposals for solutions

We understood that the main problems we were dealing and we mentioned in the section “abstract” are that people are not informed and therefore, we understood that the most effective way of informing people on the subject is the most effective way of defending animal rights.

In this way, we have developed a website that will contain various information on all the issues we are dealing with. We also managed to build a game on a programming platform so that we could draw the attention of different ages and focus on the issue of animal rights. Finally, we made a memory game that will be posted on our website and all people will have the opportunity to play it, as well as learn about the animal facts that will be featured on our game cards. In addition, we have also created a mathematical problem in relation to endangered species, which we will include in a book to further inform people involved in mathematics. The mathematical problem, website link, video game link and memory game will be presented in the Appendix 2.

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Appendix 1

Q1. What do animal welfare associations do and yours in particular?

“Animal welfare associations are fighting for animal rights. Ours is particularly motivated in four areas; in the active sector, in the cultural field, the educational part, the political sector.”

Q2. How do you think the number of stray animals will decrease?

“The answer is sterilization.”

Q3. Where should one look in order to adopt an animal?

“The right way to adopt animals is to get in touch with a breeder. The best way is to communicate with a kennel or an animal welfare charity.”

Q4. Are animals given away?

“Animals are by no means given away, animals are not objects”

Q5. What are the needs of pets? Does the law help

“The law is quite strict regarding pets, however there is no control system that helps improve the animals’ well-being.”

Q6. We hear and read on social media but also on media about aggressive animals? But what does it mean to be aggressive?

“Social media as well as many channels present dogs as well as animals in general as aggressive because of an attack on humans. Most of the time the animal has not attacked someone unintentionally.”

Q7. How can animals help vulnerable groups?

“Animals in general, in relation to humans, understand neither disability nor ugliness. In this way it is safe to say that an animal loves everyone unconditionally, and the only thing it sees in one is the love it transmits and nothing else. Therefore, bringing an animal into contact with a person who has either a problem, autistic children, or people with mental problems automatically means better socializing conditions. Vulnerable groups are also the blind, so there are dogs who are blind guides. In addition, even with a dog at home, we help our children develop empathy. Empathy means being able to step into someone else’s place and understand their need. This way, of course, the animals can help the vulnerable groups, as well as all of us.”

Q8. What about productive animals? Do they have rights?

“Productive animals are doomed to live in miserable conditions.”

Q9. What is the position of animal associations for fur animals (that is, their fur coats) and equidae?

“In our country there has been a great deal of effort for equidae, because in the past we had very bad reviews for the donkey used for transportation purposes in Santorini and Hydra. So as a country we have accepted an international outcry, animal associations all over the country have fought for it and as a result we have already improved the way we treat equidae. Now for fur animals, there has been a great campaign in our country by all animal organizations, and that is because fur animals are beaten alive. So anyone who wears fur or leather should understand that what he wears is the result of torture.”

Q10. How can we help the current situation?

“In many ways. First, adopting an animal, an animal from a kennel or even an animal association, if and when we want it. If we can't do that, talk about the animals and their rights, about the production animals, it's good to have food on them to feed on if we can, talk about neutering, get into an animal association. These are simple ways in which everyone can help the situation.”

Appendix 2

Our website;

<https://blogs.sch.gr/sdb-social-innovation/animalert/>

The Video game;

<https://scratch.mit.edu/projects/357649325>

The Memory game;

Mathematical problem;

Mathematical problem

For several years now, endangered species have been listed on the IUCN Red List. Based on this data, we created this problem based on the results for CR (critically endangered) endangered species.

- Find the percentage for each category of endangered species (with an accuracy of one decimal digit)
- Find the most populous category of endangered species and also find the category with the fewest endangered species
- The species of amphibians under extinction is expected to double by next year. Find the percentage of amphibians in 2020 if all other categories remain stable

Number of endangered species
2019

■ Mammals ■ Birds ■ Reptiles
■ Amphibians ■ Fish ■ Insects

Categories of endangered species	Number of endangered species
Mammals	203
Birds	224
Reptiles	303
Amphibians	575
Fish	549
Insects	311

